

Type and level of production provided by the requestor

Type of production: Broiler

Level: Slaughter

Keywords: Alternatively

Background context provided by the requestor

A broiler slaughterhouse using gas stunning equipment have been experiencing issues with the stunning process. In response, the company has taken action. Animals showing breathing, movement, cloaca movement, or palpebral reflex are not shackled. Furthermore, all animals are assessed following the stunner using an air pulse to stimulate them, with a trained operator monitoring responses such as eye opening, body movements and neck tension. Animals reacting to the air pulse are identified as insufficiently stunned, promptly removed from the line and re-stunned.

In addition, the processing line has been shortened in order to reduce the interval between stunning and neck cutting.

The staff performing the air pulse test is well-trained and hold the appropriate animal welfare certificates. As inadequately stunned broiler might be occasionally missed, the company has decided to add an extra waterbath stunner (WBS) to the line after the controlled atmosphere stunning (CAS) system.

As a small number of animals still show signs of consciousness after the initial stunning, the company aims to incorporate a second stunning method waterbath stunning, that follows the first stunner, CAS, into their stunning process.

Question raised by the requestor

- Is there any scientific or practical knowledge about the use of two stunning methods in succession?
- Could these interfere with each other?
- Is it still possible to properly monitor the stunning methods?

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Answer

- Introduction

Within the European Union, animal welfare at the time of slaughter, including for poultry, is laid down in Regulation (EC) No 1099/2009. This legislation establishes that stunning methods must be effective in inducing unconsciousness without causing avoidable pain, distress, or suffering and that unconsciousness should be maintained until death.

It further requires regular monitoring to verify the effectiveness of stunning. If checks reveal that an animal has not been stunned or regains consciousness, operators are required to use the back-up stunning equipment without delay and take prompt corrective actions in line with their standard operating procedures.

- Double stunning

A routine application of a second stunning method does not address the underlying cause of ineffective stunning by controlled atmosphere stunning (CAS), which represents the main animal welfare concern at the slaughterhouse under review. Further information on the CAS process is needed to identify the factors leading to a proportion of birds not being effectively stunned. In particular, the requestor did not provide information on the proportion of animals showing signs of consciousness after stunning. Relevant key parameters include the type of stunner, the sequence and characteristics of the stunning phases, gas composition and concentrations, bird density, stun-to-stick interval and other operational conditions. Such data are essential to determine the factors contributing to ineffective stunning and the associated welfare consequences.

If a bird remains conscious after CAS, and is subsequently shackled, it is at risk of experiencing fear and pain for being shackled conscious. Exposure to a waterbath stunning (WBS) in this condition may further increase welfare risks for the conscious animals, as the bird could receive painful electric shocks at the entry of the WBS, fail to become unconscious, or regain consciousness prior to neck cutting or during bleeding (EFSA 2019 and HSA 2016). For further information on pre-stun shocks in WBS of poultry, please refer to [Answer Q2E-EURCAW-Poultry-SFA-2025-005](#).

For all these reasons, WBS is not recommended as a routine second stunning method. However, it may still be used as an emergency back-up in the event of CAS system failure.

Monitoring of animal consciousness should be carried out on each bird at the exit of the CAS to ensure that only animals that are ineffectively stunned are re-stunned using the back-up method, which should be applied immediately upon detection of signs of consciousness, for example using a captive bolt device or head-only electrical stunning (HOES). For this purpose, the back-up stunning equipment should be immediately available at the point of use and applied without delay in cases of failure of the initially applied stunning method. It should be taken into account that the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) does not recommend the use of cervical dislocation as a method for stunning or killing poultry as it was highlighted in [Q2E-EURCAW-Poultry-SFA-2025-002](#).

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- **Is there any scientific or practical knowledge about the use of two stunning methods in succession?**

No scientific studies have been found in which CAS is routinely followed by WBS in poultry. Consequently, there is no scientific evidence supporting its routine application.

On the other hand, it is known that other slaughterhouses use a successive double stunning system in poultry. However, none of these systems has been evaluated by EURCAW-poultry-SFA. Nevertheless, the Centre visited a rabbit's slaughterhouse with two stunning systems used successively (HOES and an electrified plate or grid). It should be noted that rabbits and poultry are very different species, and observations in rabbits may not be directly extrapolated to poultry. Rabbits exhibited indicators of consciousness, such as vocalizations, following the application of the second stun. The conclusion was that a routine second stun does not prevent pre-stun shocks that may occur in the second stunner, nor does it guarantee effective stunning until death. For further information, please refer to [Q2E-Poultry-SFA-2025-003](#).

Scientific and practical evidence from animal welfare research supports the use of a second stunning method strictly as a corrective back-up measure, applied only to individual animals for which the first stunning method has failed or its effectiveness is in doubt, and not as a routine procedure applied to all animals.

- **Could these interfere with each other?**

As noted previously, no scientific studies have been identified in which CAS is followed by WBS in poultry.

From a theoretical perspective, the use of two stunning methods in succession could interact due to the physiological effects induced by the first method. According to EFSA (2019), CAS using carbon dioxide (CO₂) induces unconsciousness primarily through hypercapnia, with hypoxia developing secondarily as oxygen levels decline. Exposure to high concentrations of CO₂ increases blood CO₂ levels and lowers blood pH, which leads to depression of the central nervous system and a gradual loss of consciousness. In contrast, WBS delivers an immediate electrical current intended to induce instantaneous unconsciousness via an epileptic seizure.

It is currently unknown whether such a seizure can be effectively induced in a brain already depressed by CAS, and no data are available to determine the potential effects or implications for animal welfare.

- **Is it still possible to properly monitor the stunning methods?**

Under commercial conditions, the assessment of (un)consciousness following CAS and WBS relies mostly on animal-based indicators (ABIs). For these indicators to be relevant, they must be valid, feasible, and repeatable (EFSA, 2012b). There is no scientific evidence assessing the validity of monitoring indicators of consciousness when CAS and WBS stunning methods are applied consecutively.

In 2013, EFSA conducted a literature review to compile a list of ABIs to assess the state of (un)consciousness in birds after CAS. For key stage 1 (before bleeding), it was recommended assessing breathing, muscle tone, spontaneous blinking and wing flapping, as they have been reported to be highly sensitive and feasible, and proposed considering corneal or palpebral reflex and vocalisations as additional ABIs due to their low sensitivity or feasibility. For key stage 2 (during bleeding), the recommended ABIs were breathing, muscle tone and wing flapping, while corneal or palpebral reflex was considered additional ABI.

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Conclusions

- Routine application of a second stunning method to all birds does not address the underlying causes of ineffective stunning with Controlled Atmosphere Stunning (CAS), complicates the assessment of the animal's state of consciousness, and the relevant indicators of consciousness after a combination of CAS and WBS are currently unknown. It also has potential negative effects on carcass quality and does not provide additional animal welfare benefit.
- The CAS system mentioned by the requestor requires thorough evaluation to identify factors contributing to ineffective stunning. Relevant parameters include stunner type, gas composition and concentrations, characteristics of the stunning phases, bird density, stun-to-stick interval, and other operational conditions.
- Continuous monitoring of animal-based indicators (ABIs) of (un)consciousness is essential after CAS, with emphasis on the training and competence of personnel to correctly detect and interpret indicators of ineffective stunning or recovery of consciousness.
- A second stunning method must be applied only as a corrective or back-up measure for individual birds in which the first stunning method may have failed, and it should be applied as soon as possible after exiting the CAS system using appropriate equipment (e.g., captive bolt or head-only electrical stunning).
- Waterbath stunning (WBS) must be used only as an emergency in the event of CAS system failure and is not routinely applied following CAS.

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